

Synthesis of novel $MnFe_2O_4/MIL-53(Fe)/Y$ zeolite nanocomposite catalyst and its performance for the sonocatalytic degradation of organic dye contaminants

Meysam Sadeghi^{1,*} - Pourya Zarshenas² - Mohammad Mahmoudi Alemi³ - Maryam Gholami⁴

¹Department of Chemistry, Lorestan University, Khorramabad, Iran

²Faculty of Chemistry & Petroleum Sciences, Shahid Beheshti University, Tehran, Iran

³Department of Chemistry, Golestan University, Gorgan, Iran

⁴Department of Chemistry, Lorestan University, Khorramabad, Iran

ABSTRACT

In this research, the novel $MnFe_2O_4/MIL-53(Fe)/Y$ zeolite as a magnetically separable nanocomposite catalyst was successfully synthesized by the ultrasonic-assisted hydrothermal route and identified using FE-SEM, EDAX, XRD, FTIR, VSM, and AFM analyses. Subsequently, the sonocatalytic performance of the $MnFe_2O_4/MIL-53(Fe)/Y$ nanocomposite was carried out to effectively degrade the organic dye contaminants, involving methylene blue (MB), methyl orange (MO) and rhodamine B (RhB) from aqueous solution under ultrasound (US)/ H_2O_2 system. Multiple analytical factors, such as irradiation time, catalyst amount, initial dye concentration, H_2O_2 concentration, process type, and organic dye type were studied to attain the maximum sonocatalytic efficiency. Based on the obtained outcomes, the degradation efficiency reached to be 100%, 99.2% and 90.8% for MB, RhB and MO, respectively. Plus, the trapping experiments demonstrated that $\cdot OH$ radicals are the main reactive oxidative species in the degradation of these organic dyes. In conclusion, the sonocatalytic degradation synergizing the US/ H_2O_2 in the presence of $MnFe_2O_4/MIL-53(Fe)/Y$ nanocomposite reveals a great potential to evaluate the effective treatment of toxic organic dyes from effluent.

Keywords: $MnFe_2O_4/MIL-53(Fe)/Y$, nanocomposite, organic dye, degradation, $\cdot OH$ radicals.